

Modelling of transparent PV windows with Complex Fenestration Systems in TRNSYS

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Abstract

A modification for implementing transparent BIPV in TRNSYS complex fenestration system for Type56 (multi-zone building) is presented. The optical performance is modelled with bidirectional scattering distribution function and the PV effect is introduced in the energy balance window. A parametric study is carried out to evaluate the main parameters in the transparent BIPV model, concluding the PV effect needs to be included in the window energy balance and temperature dependence of efficiency needs to be considered. The model capabilities the PV glazing impact on the heating, cooling, lighting, electric output loads are shown in an office case study.

Key Innovations

- Integrated model for BIPV windows using ISO15099 standard and PV calculation.
- Parametric study on the impact of thermal mass, PV efficiency, and temperature coefficient.

Practical Implications

A BIPV model for fenestration was developed for TRNSYS, allowing for integrated calculation of thermal, lighting, and PV output loads. The PV effect was introduced in the window energy balance in order to capture its impact in the thermal loads and get a good estimation of the cell operation temperature. Hence, this development will allow to evaluate transparent BIPV solutions in windows in an integrated simulation software.

Introduction

It is already well known that buildings energy consumption is responsible of about 40% of CO₂ emissions (IEA, 2019). Then a significant reduction of buildings greenhouse gases emissions is a key goal in order to keep the global warming below the target of 1.5°C in 2050 (IPCC, 2018). In this context, Europe developed a legislative framework to promote the energy efficiency of buildings (The European Commission, 2010, 2012), so that Green Deal (The European Commission, 2019) 2050 goal of climate-neutral continent is achieved.

Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) systems are currently used as technological solution for the contribution of buildings to the energy transition (Biyik et al., 2017). BIPV replace conventional building components or materials with PV active elements. The most common are placed in the opaque elements, either by PV modules attached to the envelope or with building elements with built-in PV cells. Another option consists in the cells cladding on transparent surfaces. Semi-transparent, and more specifically, transparent BIPV are growing interest for implementation in windows, as these introduce advantages in solar gains control, daylighting, and aesthetical integration in buildings.

On this topic, a lot of research is focused in developing emerging transparent and semi-transparent PV technologies, such as thin film solar cells (TFSC) or organic PV cells (OPV), among others (Husain et al., 2018). However, this research is still mainly in the cell development stage, and little implementation studies are carried out. Therefore, the BIPV is still dominated by Si based cells, mainly semi-transparent amorphous silicon cells (Romani et al., n.d.).

The evaluation of BIPV for window application require complex modelling, as it needs to evaluate its impact in the buildings thermal and lighting loads, as well as the electricity output and occupant comfort. Hence, its simulation need accurate modelling of the optical, thermal, and electrical performance of the PV glazing in conjunction with whole building.

Currently, TRNSYS includes models only for opaque BIPV (TESS Types 563, 566, 567, 568, and 569). Moreover, the current complex fenestration system (CFS) of multi-zone building model (Type56) can accurate calculate of the glazing panes temperature, hence it can estimate the cell temperature of a PV glazing. However, it does not allow to introduce the PV effect into the window energy balance.

The aim of paper is to present a modification of CFS model in TRNSYS Type 56 for transparent BIPV. The sensitivity of the variables of the model is assessed, mainly to evaluate the impact of the temperature dependence of the PV efficiency. Then the model is implemented in a real building case with BIPV window data taken from the goals of an on-going research project.

Modelling

The modelling of the transparent BIPV window is developed with TRNSYS18 on the basis of Complex Fenestration Model (CFS) add-on for Type56 multi-zone model (Hiller & Schöttl, 2014). This allows the calculation the optical and thermal behaviour of a window composed of up to six panes including external and internal shading systems according (ISO 15099, 2003), as shown in Figure 1. The modifications to the Type56 CFS add-on are the addition of a new input consisting on a heat flux to each window pane and the addition a new outputs consisting on the individual primary solar absorption in each individual pane. On one side, the heat flux is used to introduce the PV effect on the window pane energy balance, as in Figure 1, which is a negative heat flow. Following the ISO15099, the heat flux is divided equally between the two nodes of the window pane. Hence, it effectively it reduces the solar absorption (S_i) in the window pane, as in equation1. On the other side, the individual primary solar absorption of each pane gives more detailed information from the BDSF calculations than the current TRNSYS outputs, allowing to accurately calculate the PV output as described below.

Figure 1. (ISO 15099, 2003) window energy balance.

$$\dot{S}_i = \dot{S}_{i.dir} + \dot{S}_{i.dif} - \dot{P}_{PV} \quad (1)$$

The implemented model includes the electrical output in the window energy balance. As shown in Figure 1, the CFS first calculates the solar radiation absorption in each pane (S) and the total transmittance with a bidirectional scattering distribution function (BDSF). Then it calculates the energy balance by considering two nodes per panes, which exchange heat by conduction between them, and by long wave radiation and convection with the air gap, the other panes, room, and/or outdoor ambient. The solar radiation (S) absorption is split evenly between the two nodes of the pane. The PV effect is introduced into the energy balance

with the new heat flux input introduced in the CFS model.

The radiation available ($\dot{I}_{\tau\alpha.i}$) for PV generation at each pane can be considered as sum of the transmitted and absorbed radiation in each pane. This value is not immediately available from the CFS calculations, but it can be calculated from the window solar balance outputs

by subtracting to the window total incident (NType 938 B3_QSEXT) the total reflected radiation (NType 934 B3_QBREFG) and absorbed radiation on the previous panes (the new output introduced)..

With the new inputs and outputs of Type56 configured, the PV output is calculated with an external equation block that first calculates the available radiation at each pane. Note that with these outputs, the effect of the angle of incidence is accounted through the BDSF calculations

$$\dot{I}_{\tau\alpha.i} = \dot{I}_t - R_t - \sum_0^{i-1} \dot{S}_i \quad (2)$$

Then the same equation block calculates the cell efficiency and PV output. In order to implement the PV behaviour into the window several assumptions are considered. The cell efficiency, hence the PV output, is assumed to be temperature dependent, see equation 2. Both the η_{ref} and β_T , as well as the optical properties, were assumed to be given for the whole PV pane, hence already considering all the layers of the laminate composing it.

$$\dot{P}_{PV,i} = \eta_{ref} [1 + \beta_T (\theta_n - \theta_{ref})] \dot{I}_{\tau\alpha.i} \quad (3)$$

On top of the modifications for including the BIPV effect, the CFS was also modified to be able to consider the thermal mass of the window (Hiller et al., 2019).

Reference window

In order to evaluate the proposed model, the Tech4win BIPV glass development goals are taken as reference (Tech4win, 2019). This is described as a tandem cell system absorbing in the ultra-violet and in the infra-red, while keeping a high transparency in the visible range. This corresponds to the description of a solar control glass properties, hence this type of glass is used to represent the BIPV window. The whole glazing system is a double-glass composed of the aforementioned solar control glass representing the PV glass on the outer pane and a clear glass in the inner pane, its characteristics are presented in Table 1 and Figure 2.

In order to evaluate the impact of the thermal mass into the BIPV window performance, three cases are considered in the following tests. First, the massless (ML), with static calculation of the window energy balance. Second, the massive (MS) accounting the variation of internal energy of the window with the heat capacity of the reference window. see Table 1. Finally, a double mass (DM) case is tested, for artificially simulating a window with thicker panes representing a device of cells laminated between glass layers. Note that in a real application this will result in different optical properties, yet this test will help to understand the relevance of considering the thermal mass in the transparent BIPV modelling.

Table 1. Reference BIPV window properties

Design	U [W/m ² K]	Tvis [-]	g [-]	cp [kJ/kgK]	ρ [kg/m ³]
6/16/6	1.6	0.54	0.48	0.8	2500

Figure 2. Transmittance of clear and solar control glass (greyed corresponds to visible spectrum).

Step response test

A mock-up test cell is modelled with the multi-zone building model of TRNSYS (Type56). It is designed as single air-node 3D zone with a single external wall including a window.

The behaviour of the BIPV window was evaluated under a step response test, switching from reference winter conditions (low temperatures, no solar radiation) to reference summer conditions (high temperature and incident solar radiation) according National Fenestration Rating Council conditions, as summarized in Table 2. Both the external boundary conditions and the zone parameters are controlled, only allowing free-floating of the window temperatures.

Table 2. Conditions of step response test

Parameter	Winter	Summer
External air temperature	-18°C	32°C
External radiation temperature	-18°C	32°C
External emissivity	1	1
Wind speed	5.5 m/s	2.8 m/s
Interior air temperature	21°C	24°C
External air temperature	21°C	24°C
Solar direct radiation	0 W/m ²	783 W/m ²

The cell temperature, actual efficiency, and PV output are evaluated according to the sensitivity to window thermal mass (with or without considering it), reference efficiency, and temperature coefficient. The efficiency and temperature coefficients are selected for typical values of emerging transparent PV technologies (Husain et al., 2018).

Figure 3 shows the impact of considering the thermal mass and the PV effect in the cell temperature and PV output respectively. Only the reference cases without PV and the case with η_{ref} of 0.05 and 0.1 with β_T of -0.5% are represented in the graph.

The inclusion of the PV effect on the energy balance reduces the cell temperature due to the “cooling” effect produced by the PV output. These temperature differences are proportional to the η_{ref} , as summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Step test final cell temperature.

		PV cell final temperature (°C)	T diff. (K)
η_{ref}	0	41.15	-
	0.01	40.86	-0.29
	0.025	40.43	-0.72
	0.05	39.70	-1.45
	0.1	38.24	-2.91
	0.15	36.77	-4.38

Figure 3. Cell temperature results ($\beta_T = -0.5\%$).

As also shown in Figure 3, the thermal mass influences the dynamics of the window temperature, hence it affects to PV output. The transient phase, accounting up to 95% of the step change of the cell temperature, lasts 0.7h for the normal mass case and 1.3h for the double mass case.

Once the temperature dependence of the PV efficiency is taken into account, the dynamics of the temperature cause a difference in the PV output, as shown in the different areas in Figure 4. Table 4 summarizes the energy difference of the massive and massless cases during the transient period. It shows that the β_T is the main responsible for the energy difference. However, there is an interaction effect between the thermal mass and the β_T .

Figure 4. Cell PV outputs results ($\beta_T = -0.5\%$).

Table 4. Energy difference during transient period.

	β_T	η_{ref}				
		0.01	0.025	0.05	0.1	0.15
Massive (MS)	-1	17.9%	17.8%	17.7%	17.3%	15.9%
	-0.5	8.2%	8.1%	8.0%	7.9%	7.7%
	-0.25	3.9%	3.9%	3.9%	3.8%	3.7%
	0	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	0.25	-3.6%	-3.6%	-3.5%	-3.5%	-3.4%
	0.5	-7.0%	-6.9%	-6.8%	-6.7%	-6.5%
	1	-12.9%	-12.8%	-12.7%	-12.4%	-12.1%
Double mass (DM)	-1	19.3%	19.2%	19.0%	18.0%	17.6%
	-0.5	8.8%	8.7%	8.6%	8.5%	8.0%
	-0.25	4.2%	4.2%	4.1%	4.0%	3.8%
	0	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	0.25	-3.9%	-3.9%	-3.8%	-3.7%	-3.6%
	0.5	-7.5%	-7.4%	-7.3%	-7.2%	-7.0%
	1	-13.9%	-13.8%	-13.6%	-13.8%	-13.4%

Dynamic test

A test cell is developed according to IEA Task 34 exercise 3 (Loutzenhiser et al., 2007). The base case is modified to include the BIPV window described in the previous section.

The model is run for an annual simulation considering ideal convective heating and cooling system, with set-points of 21°C and 26°C, respectively. The annual PV output, heating, and cooling loads sensitivity is evaluated to the parameters of window thermal mass (with or without considering it), η_{ref} , and temperature coefficient. The boundary conditions are considered for Madrid (Spain) climate, using hourly weather file from Meteonorm.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the behaviour of the window cell temperature and PV output for a typical summer and winter day, respectively. As expected, the cell maximum temperature is directly influenced by the η_{ref} , with reduced temperature with increasing efficiency. However, the graphs show that considering the thermal mass in the calculations have minimal impact on the cell temperature, below 0.5°C in both in MS and DM compares to massless case.

Figure 5. Dynamic test typical summer day ($\beta_T = -0.5$).

Further analysis is shown in Figure 7, where the impact of η_{ref} and β_T on the annual cooling and heating demands, as well as total PV output is represented. It is important to highlight that the test case studied results in clearly cooling dominated case due to its small surface, South oriented façade, and non-shaded window. Yet the results are indicative of the impact of the studied parameter.

First, PV output is, as expected, proportional to the η_{ref} , moreover it also influences on the cooling load with reductions of 1.2% and 2.5% for $\eta_{ref}=0.05$ and $\eta_{ref}=0.1$, respectively. The β_T only has a significant impact on the PV output, with energy difference up to 2.5% and 5.1% for the $\beta_T=-0.5$ and $\beta_T=-1$ respectively. The inclusion of the thermal mass in the energy balance mainly affects the heating load, with differences of 2.7% and 6% for the MS and DM cases, respectively. However, an interaction effect between thermal mass and β_T was observed.

Figure 6. Dynamic test typical winter day ($\beta_T = -0.5$).

Figure 7. Dynamic test annual energy results.

Case study

An experimentally validated model of an office building, see Figure 8, is used to compare the performance of a

BIPV solution compared to current façade solution.

Figure 8. Reference building.

In order to focus the analysis, a single office room on the second floor is evaluated. Its characteristics are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. Room geometry.

Length	11.21 m
Depth	9.58 m
Height	3.47 m
Floor surface	107.39 m ²
Façade surface	33.24 m ²
Window surface	18.48 m ²
Window to Wall Ratio (WWR)	47.5%
Orientation	South

Table 6. Construction elements characteristics.

Surface	Composition	Thick [m]	U [W/m ² K]
Roof	Crushed pottery Cellular concrete Expanded cork Reinforced concrete slab Air (suspended ceiling) Aluminium ceiling	0.64	0.32
Façade	Lacquered aluminium Rock wool Galvanized steel	0.104	0.32
Floor	Ceramic tile Cement mortar Sand Reinforced concrete slab Air (suspended ceiling) Aluminium ceiling	0.415	2.4
Inner walls	Gypsum board Rock wool Gypsum board	0.13	0.44

Both the reference and BIPV cases consist of a double glazed window with internal movable textile shade, modelled as a diffusing shade material with 0.4 visible transmittance (equivalent to a shading factor of 0.6). The characteristics of the reference and BIPV window are presented in Table 7, note that both window have very similar characteristics except for T_{vis} . The BIPV window has a η_{ref} of 0.1 and a β_T of -0.5. A controller closes the shade if the incident radiation is above 180 W/m² and open it again if it goes below 160 W/m². Notice that Type56 daylighting model based on DAYSIM does not use the BDSF model geometrical shading features (such as venetian and perforated blinds) from the CFS add-on. If this can of shading are to be used, daylighting calculation with RADIANCE models can be introduced

as input to the TRNSYS simulation (Brembilla et al., 2019). The DAYSIM approach integrated in Type56 is used in the current simulation to show the general capabilities of the BIPV model. Hence only the diffusing shade with two position (shaded / unshaded) is considered.

The internal gains, ventilation, and temperature set-points are associated to the occupancy of the building, see Figure 9.

Occupants and equipment gains are proportional to the occupancy fraction, while ventilation is on if there is any kind of occupation. Light gains depend on the lighting control. Table 8 and Table 9 summarize the nominal values of internal gains and air change rates.

Table 7. Window characteristics

Case	Design	Gla ss U	Tvis	SHG C	Fram e U	Fram e fr
Ref.	8/15/6 +5	1.3	0.74	0.53	2.3	15%
BIPV	6/16/6	1.6	0.54	0.48	2.3	15%

The set-points of the room are 21°C and 26°C for heating and cooling, respectively, with setback temperatures of 17°C and 30°C for non-occupancy periods.

The lighting is controlled under daylighting on-off strategy, with an illuminance point of 500 lux, a threshold for turning the light on of 300 lux. In order to evaluate the illuminance, the average value of one control point located at 1m above the centre of the room was used.

The simulations are run under Madrid (Spain) weather conditions, using hourly weather file from Meteonorm. The cooling, heating, and lighting energy demands are converted to primary energy. The supply systems were considered to be a natural gas boiler with efficiency of 0.95 and a chiller SEER of 2.2. The natural gas and electricity primary energy factor are 1.1 and 2.5 kWh_p/kWh_f, respectively, according to (ISO 52000, 2019). Usually, on-site renewables, such as the PV output, are considered to have a primary energy factor of 1 by itself. However, for calculating the building primary energy factor, the PV output is used to reduce the electricity import from the grid, hence the grid electricity primary energy factor of 2.5 kWh_p/kWh_f is considered.

Figure 9. Occupancy profile.

Table 8. Internal gains.

Type	Gain [W/m ²]	Radiative fraction
Occupants	6	0.5
Equipment	4.5	0.2

Light	15.31	0.7
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Table 9. Air changes rates.

Air stream	Air changes [1/h]
Infiltration	0.32
Ventilation	0.6

Annual simulation

The results of the annual simulation are presented in Figure 10. Overall, the primary energy consumption with the BIPV window increases by a 11.1 %. However, once considering the PV production, the total primary energy consumption decreases by 26.9%.

Figure 10. Annual primary energy results of case study.

Analysing the individual energy demands, the main difference between the reference and BIPV cases is the lighting energy consumption. The BIPV window considered has less visible transmittance than the reference case one, which results in less daylighting and hence a 17.7 % increase in lighting energy use. On the other side, the impact of the BIPV window on the thermal loads is minimal, with a decrease of 1.1 % of the cooling demand and an increase of the heating demand of 1.5 %. The results of the thermal loads are mainly caused due to the high internal heat gains of the building. These are estimated to represent a 55% of the cooling demand and to reduce a 54% the heating demand.

Discussion

The results of the step and dynamic test show that it is important to consider the PV effect into the window energy balance, as well as the importance of the temperature dependence of the efficiency. In contrast, the thermal mass will only have a relevant impact on the heating load in most cases. With the obtained time-constants, the dynamics of a window are still faster than the dynamics of the boundary conditions (weather and other building components). Hence, the cell temperature and the resulting PV output are barely affected. However, the parametric analysis identifies an interaction effect between thermal mass and temperature coefficients.

The office buildings are considered an ideal target for BIPV solutions because of the amount of glazed surface and intensive energy demand. The case study shows the impact of the BIPV window in such buildings, resulting in a potential for overall primary energy reduction, mainly related to the PV production. However, the selected BIPV window caused an increase a lighting consumption, as a relatively low transparency glass was used. Moreover, the case study showed that the impact in the thermal loads is minimal in buildings with intensive heat gains. However, the evaluation in the present paper is limited by the simplification of the BIPV window to a solar control one. The specific characteristics of each of the BIPV technology, such as state of the art amorphous silicon thin film or emerging ones such as perovskite and organic cells, will have different advantages in terms of solar control, daylighting, and PV output. Nevertheless, it shows that the impact of this systems can be carried out with the current model if the optical properties, nominal efficiency, and temperature coefficient are provided.

The design of the façade using BIPV window needs to optimize the glazing solution, the shading design, and daylighting control in order to achieve the best performance. The window-to-wall ratio and aspect factor of the building are also important parameters influencing the impact of the BIPV window into the building. The developed model allows for detailed calculation of all this aspects, allowing for integrated calculation of the PV output, daylighting, and thermal loads, including detailed shading configuration with the BSDF, all integrated in a 3D building model.

Finally, the modification to Type56 were done to ensure that transparent BIPV can be modelled. However, the inputs are left flexible to allow modelling other phenomena, with the heat flux allowing positive and negative values and being independent to actual incident irradiation.

Conclusions

A BIPV model for fenestration applications was developed for TRNSYS, using detailed BSDF glazing modelling according ISO15099 and PV effect included in the energy balance. The modifications to Type56 CFS add-on allowing the implementation of this model are expected to become a new feature in future versions of TRNSYS.

A parametric study is carried out to study the impact of considering the thermal mass, the PV efficiency, and temperature coefficient. The conclusions are that it is important to consider the PV effect into the window energy balance and the temperature dependence of efficiency. The thermal mass might only be relevant in cases with thick glass (multi-laminated) and high temperature coefficients.

Finally, the implemented case study in an office building highlighted shows the need to balance the impact of the BIPV window on the lighting, cooling, and heating loads, as well as in the PV output. This makes relevant the optimization of the envelope design in terms of window-to-wall ratio, glazing systems (transparency and solar

factor), and shading systems. The lighting design and control strategy will also affect the optimization. The evaluation is limited by the assumption of the BIPV to behave as a solar control glass. While the model allows to compare different BIPV technologies, the goal of the current article is to show to evaluate to model itself. Next steps will consist on implementing actual data from BIPV windows.

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Nomenclature

Symbol	Description
η	Efficiency [-]
β_T	Temperature coefficient [%/°C]
θ	Temperature [°C]
\dot{S}	Absorbed radiation [W/m ²]
\dot{T}	Transmitted radiation [W/m ²]
\dot{R}	Reflected radiation [W/m ²]
\dot{i}	Incident radiation [W/m ²]
\dot{P}_{PV}	PV output [W/m ²]
$\dot{i}_{\tau\alpha,i}$	Total transmitted and absorbed radiation [W/m ²]
Sub	Description
i	Window pane
t	Total
ref	Nominal conditions

References

- Biyik, E., Araz, M., Hepbasli, A., Shahrestani, M., Yao, R., Shao, L., Essah, E., Oliveira, A. C., del Caño, T., Rico, E., Lechón, J. L., Andrade, L., Mendes, A., & Athi, Y. B. (2017). A key review of building integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) systems. In *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal* (Vol. 20, Issue 3, pp. 833–858). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestch.2017.01.009>
- Brembilla, E., Chi, D. A., Hopfe, C. J., & Mardaljevic, J. (2019). Evaluation of climate-based daylighting techniques for complex fenestration and shading systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 203, 109454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.109454>
- Hiller, M., Gut, M., & Holst, S. (2019). CFS model improvement based on measured data of a 1:1 scale test mock-up. *Proceedings of the 16th IBPSA Conference*.
- Hiller, M., & Schöttl. (2014). Modellierung Komplexer Verglasungssysteme in TRNSYS. *Proceedings from BauSIM2014: German Building Performance Simulation Conference*, 26–28.
- Husain, A. A. F., Hasan, W. Z. W., Shafie, S., Hamidon, M. N., & Pandey, S. S. (2018). A review of transparent solar photovoltaic technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 94(July), 779–791.
- IEA. (2019). *Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction 2019 – Analysis*.
- IPCC. (2018). *Global Warming of 1.5 °C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change*. <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>
- ISO 15099. (2003). *Thermal performance of windows, doors and shading devices – Detailed calculations*. International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO 52000. (2019). *Energy performance of building - Overarching EPB assessment*. International Organization for Standardization.
- Loutzenhiser, P. G., Manz, H., Felsmann, C., Strachan, P. A., & Maxwell, G. M. (2007). An empirical validation of modeling solar gain through a glazing unit with external and internal shading screens. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 27(2–3), 528–538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2006.06.016>
- Romani, J., Ramos, A., & Salom, J. (n.d.). Review of transparent and semi-transparent building integrated photovoltaics for fenestration applications modelling in building simulation. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Submitted December 2019).
- Tech4win. (2019). *Disruptive sustainable technologies for next generation pv windows*. EU H2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement no. 826002.
- The European Commission. (2010). *Energy performance of buildings directive* | Energy. https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en
- The European Commission. (2012). *Energy efficiency directive*.
- The European Commission. (2019). *The European Green Deal*. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/e_n/ip_19_6691